

Concept of *Yarqān Suddī* in the Unani System of Medicine: A Correlation with Cholestatic Jaundice and Future Prospects

Tooba Bilal Wani¹, Shameem Ahmad Rather²

¹PG Scholar, Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine, Srinagar

²Professor Moalajat, Regional Research Institute of Unani Medicine, Srinagar.

ABSTRACT

Cholestatic jaundice, a condition that is characterised by the impaired bile flow and subsequent hepatic injury, remains a therapeutic challenge in modern medicine, with limited options for patients unresponsive to conventional treatments like ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA). Unani Medicine describes an analogous condition termed *Yarqān Suddī*, attributing it to the stagnation of yellow bile (*Ṣafrā'*) due to hepatic obstruction (*Sudad al-Jigar*). Classical books describe its etiology and pathology that closely correlate with contemporary understandings of cholestasis, including intrahepatic ductal dysfunction, oxidative stress, and fibrosis progression. Unani pharmacology offers plenty of herbal interventions, such as *Berberis vulgaris* (*Zarishk*) and *Portulaca oleracea* (*Tukhm-i-Khurfā*), which demonstrate choleric, anti-inflammatory, and hepato-protective properties, aligning with modern targets like FXR modulation and bile acid homeostasis. Compound formulations (e.g., *Sāfūf-i-Bazūr*) can be used as multi-target approach, addressing both symptoms and systemic toxicity. Despite its potential, the integration of Unani therapies into mainstream hepatology needs validation on a scientific basis. All the data were collected from classical Unani texts, including Canon of Medicine (*Al-Qānūn fi'l Ṭibb* by Ibn Sina), *Iksīr-i-A'zam* (Hakim Azam Khan), *Dhakhīra Khwarizm Shāhī* (Ismail Jurjānī), *Al-Qarābādīn* (Hk Kabeer-u-din), and *Kāmil al-Ṣanā'a* (Ibn Majūsi), for the Unani descriptions of cholestasis and its management. For the contemporary concept indexed journals were searched using databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Elsevier, with keywords including "cholestasis," "Unani medicine and herbal hepatoprotectives."

Keywords: Yarqān Suddī, *Berberis vulgaris*, Hepatic obstruction, Cholestatic jaundice.

INTRODUCTION

The term "Cholestasis", which literally translates to "bile stoppage" was introduced in the 1930's. It was first used to describe cirrhosis caused by blockage of the smallest bile ducts. It was an effort to provide a broad word for conditions where the extra-hepatic bile ducts were normal but the histologic results showed obstructive jaundice. Later, the term included any liver disease marked by decreased bile flow. Both major (extra-hepatic cholestasis) and small, microscopic (intra-hepatic cholestasis) duct lesions were included in the definition. Accompanying this, the diagnostic characteristic for cholestasis changed from jaundice, a physical finding, to abnormal serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP), a laboratory test.¹

Hence, Cholestatic liver diseases (CLD's) refer to a group of disorders in which jaundice and reduced bile flow are the primary clinical features. These conditions are typically indicated by elevated levels of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) or Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), along with diminished bile secretion and, eventually, a rise in bilirubin.²

The next step involves locating the blockage in bile flow and to distinguish between intra-hepatic and extra-hepatic cholestasis. Though the cholestatic liver disease is composed of a wide spectrum of the diseases and the pathophysiological processes differ among these disorders, but all of these can cause fibrosis and eventually advance to end-stage liver disease, requiring a liver transplant together. Hence, these conditions contribute to substantial health and

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economic challenges. In Western nations, cholestatic liver diseases are the third most common reason for liver transplants—one of the costliest medical interventions in modern healthcare.³

For some of the frequently occurring cholestatic liver disorders, therapeutic choices are still very less to prevent the progression. Though, ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) is commonly used, yet the lack of effective alternatives presents a challenge for patients who do not respond to UDCA. This determines the urgent need for novel therapeutic strategies and early intervention to prevent the risk of the liver transplantation. Moreover, UDCA has limited efficacy in other cholestatic disorders, such as primary sclerosing cholangitis (PSC), where it may even be harmful at high doses, and in genetic conditions like progressive familial intrahepatic cholestasis (PFIC)⁴. Given these limitations, second-line therapies need to be actively investigated. Importantly, early therapeutic intervention is critical, as UDCA's benefits are most pronounced in early-stage disease, whereas delayed treatment often results in poorer outcomes due to irreversible fibrosis⁵.

Unani Medicine, also called Greco-Arab Medicine, has been used for a long time to reduce pain, treat illness, and support good health.

Hepatic obstruction (*Suda jigar*) is a well-documented condition in Unani Medicine, encompassing various hepatic disorders characterised by the obstructions at various anatomical locations.¹² Among these, cholestatic jaundice (*Yarqān Suddī*) holds particular significance, where the blockage may occur either in the biliary tract between the liver and gallbladder or, as some classical texts describe, deep within the liver parenchyma itself (Intra-hepatic cholestasis). This latter presentation, owing to its anatomical complexity, often renders the condition particularly challenging to treat, as mentioned by *Mohd Tabri* in *Moalajat Buqratiya*.⁶

2. Modern perspective of intrahepatic cholestasis and correlation with *Yarqān Suddī*:

2.1 Are the basic descriptions of cholestasis and *Yarqān Suddī* similar?

The biliary canaliculi in the liver are thin tubes that are lined by the hepatocytes. They collect the bile and empty it into large bile ductules and the ducts. Bile contains specific acids (including cholic and chenodeoxycholic acid) that break down dietary fats into smaller droplets, facilitating the action of digestive enzymes and promoting the uptake of vitamins A, D, E, and K in the intestines⁷. Hence, bile holds significance in digestion. Hepatocyte dysfunction (lining the biliary canaliculi) can result in the retention of bile acids, bilirubin, and other biliary components referred to as intrahepatic cholestasis⁸. The condition may develop due to a broad range of triggers, such as inherited mutations, hormonal effects, drug-induced hepatotoxicity, and various liver pathologies.^{9,10}

In Unani literature, there is a remarkable description correlating with intrahepatic cholestasis. It's mentioned that sometimes jaundice (*Yarqān*) is secondary to obstruction or "*Suda*" within the liver itself (and sometimes outside). Within the liver, obstruction is occasionally in the (vessels/channels ("*Urūq*") that spread throughout the liver parenchyma¹¹. Unlike blood-carrying vessels, these *Urūq* do not contain blood but instead play a role in the metabolism of chyme (*Tabakh Kailoos*) and the processing of humours (*akhlāt*)^{12,13}. This determines the analogy to the stasis in biliary canaliculi, spread within the liver and the significance of bile in the digestion and metabolism as well.

2.2 Are the outcomes analogous in the Unani literature and the Modern literature?

It was first suggested that bile acids' direct cytolytic/detergent actions in cholestasis cause hepatocyte death. New research supports the idea that inflammation plays a major role in cholestatic liver damage¹⁴.

The accumulation of bile acids within hepatocytes triggers oxidative stress and apoptotic cell death, which in turn activates hepatic stellate cells, leading to progressive liver fibrosis¹⁵. Without intervention, this fibrotic process advances to cirrhosis, characterized by the development of portal hypertension and its life-threatening complications including ascites². Fever can also be present in cirrhosis, often reflecting a serious underlying

complication, most commonly infection due to immune dysfunction¹⁶.

Analogous to it, in classical Unani texts⁶, the author mentions that if obstruction or the *Suda jigar* doesn't resolve, it leads to the prolonged stagnation of yellow bile (*Ṣafrā'*) in the liver (*Jigar*). It has been described as severely dangerous, as the liver cannot tolerate the deleterious effects of retained bile or *Ṣafrā'*. The damage can manifest as fever (*Ḥummā*), progressing to hepatic inflammation (*Warm-i-Jigar*) and then progressive hardening (*Salābat-i-Kabid*) - a remarkable parallel to modern concepts of cholestasis-induced fibrosis and cirrhosis. *Mohd Tabri* documents that there is the subsequent involvement of the spleen (*Tihāl*) and abdominal fluid accumulation or *Istisqā'*.⁶ perfectly correlate with the contemporary understanding of portal hypertension complications, including splenomegaly and ascites. This Unani description, discussed centuries before modern hepatology, accurately describes the progression from intrahepatic cholestasis to end-stage liver disease and its systemic consequences.

2.3 Whether the review of *Yarqān Suddī* will enrich Modern Pharmacological modalities to lessen the burden of disease:

Cholestasis remains a challenging condition to treat, with limited therapeutic options available. Ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) is the first-line therapy, but a significant number of patients do not show a response. Obeticholic acid (OCA), a potent farnesoid X receptor (FXR) agonist, has emerged as a second-line treatment, approved by the FDA in 2016. While OCA is a valuable treatment option for cholestasis, its high cost and side effects restrict its widespread use. The latter can lead to pruritus, may also worsen lipid profiles or cause hepatotoxicity in advanced cirrhosis. Some patients still progress despite treatment with OCA¹⁷

Liver transplantation remains one of the few available options for severe cholestatic patients without proper treatment¹⁸. Therefore, there is an urgent medical need to identify new molecules that can enhance bile transport and provide hepatoprotection against cholestasis by reducing bile acid accumulation.

Natural products have attracted considerable attention in pharmaceutical research due to their diverse chemical structures and wide range of biological functions. Their use can be traced back to the earliest traditional healing systems, including Chinese medicine, Ayurveda, and Unani, which relied on materials derived from plants, animals, fungi, and microorganisms. Over the past century, advancements in chemistry and pharmacology have transformed these natural remedies into more structured, standardized, and scientifically validated medicinal systems.¹⁹ While Western medicine has only recently recognized the therapeutic benefits of ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) for liver diseases, traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) has utilized it for centuries. Early preparations were rudimentary, consisting of dried bile extracted from black bears.²⁰

In recent years, numerous natural products have shown promising therapeutic effects against liver diseases globally. Cholestasis involves a complex interplay of transporter dysfunction, oxidative stress, inflammation, and immune disruption, highlighting the therapeutic strategies that act upon multiple pathways. Herbal drugs exhibit multi-targeted activity, acting on various biological pathways as a result of their complex and diverse phytochemical composition. The review of the detailed descriptions of liver obstruction (*Suda jigar*), cholestasis (*Yarqān Suddī*) and the respective treatments in Unani texts will expand the field of potential therapeutics in addition to the dietary modifications and lifestyle practices. Unani's extensive literature of multiple herbs specifically indicated for cholestasis, many of which need to be scientifically studied, though literature has already specified their efficacy.

3. The Etiopathogenesis and treatment of hepatic obstruction (*Sudad al-Kabid*) as mentioned in Unani literature

3.1 Etiology and correlation:

Bile production is an important hepatic function whose disruption leads to cholestasis. It is caused by multiple etiologies, including infections, autoimmune conditions, metabolic disturbances, and genetic abnormalities. Proper bile secretion requires both functional membrane transport proteins and

anatomically intact biliary structures that maintain secretory capacity².

The cause of the intrahepatic cholestasis is either the viscous matter (*Ghalīd Mādda*) in the biliary passages or hepatic inflammation (*Waram-i-Jigar*) compressing upon the passages. In the absence of excessive matter or inflammation, it may be the simple functional disorder, with no abnormal structural or biochemical deformity (*Sue-i-Mizāj*) that causes the constriction (*Inkibaz*) of biliary passages. Rarely, the constriction can be congenital (*Khalqī*) as well as structural (*Sue-Tarqīb*)¹³. They rightly correlate to the diet induced cholestasis (functional) and the biliary atresia (congenital and structural). The outcome of all the etiological factors is the disruption of expulsive faculty (*Quwatt-i-Dāfiya*) and digestive faculty (*Quwatt-i-Hādima*) of the liver¹². Hence the classical Unani concept of hepatic obstruction (*Sudah Jigar*) closely resembles with modern understandings of cholestasis: Liver inflammation (*Waram-i-Jigar*), mirroring autoimmune or infectious cholangiopathies, Biliary constriction (*Inqibāz*), comparable to strictures or genetic defects in bile duct formation. These disturbances impair the liver's expulsive faculty or *Quwatt-i-Dāfiya* and digestive faculty (or *Quwatt-i-Hādima*), leading to systemic toxicity and malabsorption, a pathophysiology now explained at the molecular level as bile has both the excretory and digestive functions²¹.

3.2 Pathogenesis and clinical manifestations:

Ibn Majosi has described that secondary to the cholestasis (*yarqān Suddī*) the bile (*ṣafrā'*) scatters throughout the body, leading to yellow discoloration of the skin and eyes²². The diagnosis of jaundice due to bile stasis (due to various causes) is to be done by common features and the differentiating features. The features common to all types are the following:

- The patient tends to feel heaviness at the site of liver.
- The stool is whitish in color¹².
- Every organ of the body has abundance of bile or *Ṣafrā'*. The effect on muscles *azla* manifests as restlessness⁶.

For the absolute diagnosis or the cause of cholestasis (*yarqān suddī*) can be determined by the associated features:

- Liver inflammation (*waram*): It presents with a distinctive pulling sensation associated with the pain at the liver site;
- Diet-related obstruction (*inkibāz*) reveals dietary history of astringent substances known to cause biliary strictures or obstruction, such as hard water or certain types of clay. These constipating agents (*Qābiḍ*) could lead to narrowing of the bile ducts, impairing proper bile flow. The patients with congenital (*khalqī*) narrowing of biliary passages exhibit the long history jaundice from the early childhood¹³.

Mohammad Tabri has documented the equivalent of systemic toxicity resulting from bile spread in the body. Once yellow bile enters the bloodstream, it can reach the brain (*dimāgh*) via nutrients (*ghida*) pathways, leading to headaches⁶. This aligns with the modern understanding that bilirubin can cross the blood-brain barrier. According to Galen, the liver is prone to fibrosis. Once hardening sets in completely, it is impossible to reverse it. Thereby, the primary prevention is more significant²³. The stagnation of the bile inside liver makes it prone to fibrosis⁶. This highlights the importance of early intervention in cholestasis (*Yarqān suddī*). *Raban Tabri* says that liver obstruction (*Sudad al-Kabid*), if persistent, leads to inflammation of the liver (*iltihāb-al-jigar*)⁶, while *Ibn Masoya* warns that persistent inflammation of the liver (*Waram-i-Kabid*) leads to abdominal fluid accumulation (*Istisqā'*)²³. Hence, the symptoms of fibrosis (*Tahajjur*) and ascites (*Istisqā'*) will set in the late stages if the condition is not treated early.

3.3. Search of specific use of Unani drugs as anticholestatic:

3.2 and 3.3 have been studied in the above section mainly with determining their correlativity hence extracting the hypothesis from Unani pathology and hence pharmacotherapy for the further research.

3.3.1 The drugs documented to have efficacy:

Herbal interventions can be selected to target multiple pathological pathways, including the anti cholestatic, and hepato-protective (or anti-inflammatory agents), which may help prevent the progression to hepatic fibrosis.

Classical Unani texts describe numerous drugs that promote the bile flow. *Hakim Zakariya Razi* has mentioned the use of drugs like *Saussurea costus* (*Qust*), *Polyporus officinalis* (*Gharīqūn*), *Prunus amygdalus* var. *amara* (*Bādām Talkh*), *Agrimonia eupatorias* (*Ghāfi*)

The other herbs documented to have anticholestatic activity include *Cucumis sativus* (*Tukhm Khayarain*) *Portulaca oleracea* (*Tukhm-i-Khurfa*), *Berberis vulgaris* (*Zarishk*), *Adiantum capillus-veneris* (*Parsiyaoshān*), *Chenopodium album* (*Tukhm-i-Bathwā*)¹².

In addition to single herbs, compound formulations are abundantly described in classical literature, many of which are designed to target multiple pathological pathways as mentioned in *Al Qarābadīn*²⁸ (Table 1)

COMPOUND	DOSAGE	INGREDIENTS
<i>Sāfūf-i-Bazūr</i>	10 g	<i>Berberis vulgaris</i> , <i>Cichorium intybus</i> , <i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> , <i>Apium graveolens</i> , <i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> , <i>Crocus sativus</i> , <i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i> , <i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> , <i>Artemesia absinthinum</i> , <i>Rheum emodi</i> , <i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> , <i>Kerria lacca</i>
<i>Sāfūf-i-Behdāna</i>	3-5 g	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> , <i>Bambusa arundinacea</i> , <i>Bole armeniac</i> , <i>Rosa damascena</i> , <i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i> , <i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> , <i>Cydonia oblonga</i> , <i>Cucumis sativus</i> , Starch powder <i>Kerria lacca</i>
<i>Sharbat-i-Azkar</i>	24-48 g	<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i> , <i>Cinnamomum verum</i> , <i>Acorus calamus</i> , <i>Commiphora opobalsamum</i> , <i>Rheum emodi</i> , <i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> , <i>Andropogon schoenanthus</i> (Flower and root), <i>Artemesia absinthinum</i> , <i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> , <i>Apium graveolens</i> , <i>Pimpinella anisum</i> , <i>Rosa damascena</i> , <i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>
<i>Sharbat-i-Ambarbāris</i>	24-48 g	<i>Asarum europaeum</i> , <i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> , <i>Pimpinella anisum</i> , <i>Polypodium vulgare</i> , <i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> , <i>Rosa damascena</i> , <i>Rheum emodi</i> , <i>Kerria lacca</i> , <i>Crocus sativa</i> , <i>Santalum album</i> , <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> , <i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> , <i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> , <i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i> , <i>Berberis vulgaris</i> , <i>Portulaca oleracea</i>

3.4 Principles of treatment (*Usūl-i-Ilaj*):

Ibn Sina has enunciated in *Al-canon* in the general Management that bile stasis requires the therapeutic agent possessing these key properties: moderate purgative effects (*Mutawassit al-Ishāl*) and diuretic activity (*Mudirr-i-Bawl*). The optimal approach involves first using deobstruent drugs (*Mufattih*) that remove blockage from a luminal organ of the body to restore physiological pathways, followed by drugs that cleanse the surface of organs (*jali*), and substances to clear accumulated morbid matter. Then, the purgation and diuresis flush out the morbid matter, cleansed from the biliary passages and present in the blood¹³. After the general management, the causes are addressed by absolute therapeutic modalities. If it is diet-induced (clay, mineral water), bring into use compound formulations like *Arq-i-Shahitra*, *Sharbat-*

i-Dīnār, *Habb-i-Mushil* to flush out the morbid dietary matter through the stool. In case of *Waram-i-Kabid* (being the cause), resolvent drugs (*Radā'ī Adviya*) must be used to prevent the insults of the inflammation in the liver or fibrosis (*Tahajjur*)^{12,13}.

Discussion:

The concept of *Yarqān Suddī* in Unani Medicine is typically parallel to modern understandings of cholestatic jaundice, In Unani texts, *Yarqān Suddī* is described as a condition arising from the stagnation of yellow bile or *Ṣafrā'* due to obstruction (*Sudad al-Jigar*), whether within the liver's parenchyma or in the biliary tract. This mirrors the modern definition of cholestasis, where impaired bile flow in the biliary canaliculi, ultimately leads to the accumulation of bile acids, oxidative stress, and eventual hepatocellular

injury. Both systems recognize the progression from bile stasis to systemic complications such as jaundice, fibrosis, and ascites, reflecting a shared pathophysiological framework. The Unani describes on channels (*Urūq*) as the passages for bile metabolism aligns with modern histology, where biliary canaliculi and ductules play a central role in bile secretion and the digestion (*Tabakh Kailoos*). This highlights the ancient Unani scholars had explained mechanisms of bile flow disruption long before the microscopic inventions.

Modern medicine faces significant challenges in treating cholestatic disorders, particularly for patients unresponsive to first-line therapies like ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) or obeticholic acid (OCA). The limitations of these drugs—high cost, side effects, and uncertain efficacy—create a need for alternative treatments. Unani medicine has a plethora of herbal interventions that can target multiple pathways in cholestasis, from enhancing bile flow to produce inflammation and oxidative stress, owing to their multiple bioactive molecules. For example the contemporary studies revealed, *Berberis vulgaris* (*Zarishk*) (already documented in Unani texts as a choleric agent), contains berberine, a compound known to modulate Farnesoid X receptor (FXR) pathways²⁵. Similarly, *Portulaca oleracea* (*Tukhm-i-Khurfa*) can improve the bile flow through its omega-3 fatty acids²⁶, and *Agrimonia eupatoria* (*Ghafis*) provides hepatoprotection by inhibition of oxidation²⁷ as established by some recent studies. Along these herbs the compound formulations like *Sāfūf-i-Bazūr* or *Sharbat-i-Azkhar* have been mentioned in classical Unani texts as anticholestatic formulations highlight the Unani wisdom of multi-target therapy. The integration of Unani pharmacology into modern hepatology could fill the gaps, particularly for cholestasis or early-stage disease prevention. However, this requires rigorous scientific validation, including pharmacokinetic studies and randomized controlled trials to standardize dosing and assess safety. By correlating the ancient literature with modern, the treatment mentioned in the classical books for *Yarqān Suddi* may add to the therapeutic options for cholestatic diseases. Future research should focus on isolating bioactive compounds from Unani herbs and evaluating their efficacy. The integration between Unani Scholars and modern

hepatologists could design randomized trials comparing compound formulations with standard therapies.

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Author's contribution

Tooba Bilal: Conceptualization, Methodology, Original draft preparation,

Shameem Ahmad Rather: Data curation, Visualization, Supervision, Reviewing and Editing.

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